

Universal Xalqaro Ilmiy Jurnal

Jurnalning bosh sahifasi: <https://universaljurnal.uz>

Universal International Scientific Journal

e-ISSN: [3060-4540 \(online\)](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14024875)

Year: 2024 Issue: 1 Volume: 7

Published: 20.10.2024 <https://universaljurnal.uz>

International indexes

GOOGLE SCHOLAR

CROSSREF (OAK BAZA)

ZENODO

OPEN AIRE

EUROPUB

RESEARCHGATE (OAK BAZA)

SJIF

Nabiyeva Xatiraxon

Andijan Region National Center for Training
Pedagogues in New Methodologies, Teacher of Technology
Uzbekistan

USING THE 4 K MODEL IN TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

Abstract: This article presents ideas on creating a 4K model for teachers of the technology of general education schools and conducting classes based on the 4K model.

Key words: 4K model, collaboration, creative thinking, critical thinking, logical thinking.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada umumta'lim maktablari texnologiyasi o'qituvchilari uchun 4K modelini yaratish va 4K modeli asosida darslarni o'tkazish bo'yicha g'oyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: 4K modeli, hamkorlik, ijodiy fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, mantiqiy fikrlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены идеи по созданию модели 4К для учителей технологии общеобразовательных школ и проведения занятий на основе модели 4К.

Ключевые слова: модель 4К, совместная работа, творческое мышление, критическое мышление, критическое мышление, логическое мышление.

Language: English

Citation: Nabiyeva, X. USING THE 4 K MODEL IN TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS. Universal International Scientific Journal, 1(7), 49–51. Retrieved from <https://universaljurnal.uz/index.php/jurnal/article/view/1160>

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14024875>

Nowadays, young people should be strong and competitive in terms of moral and education. They should reach the world level with their knowledge and skills and show the power of our country to the whole world. There is a lot to say about supporting the youth of our country in every way. Work on creating the necessary conditions for them to acquire modern knowledge and grow into a mature spiritual person continues consistently.

An important guarantee of the country's progress is considered to be the strong knowledge of the people. No country has risen to the level of great development without relying on its intellectual strength and capabilities, without developing spiritual, intellectual and moral values in human thinking, without awakening the national spirit of society. Changes in this regard in our country are commendable.

The great poet Firdausi writes:

This is the moment when I fell in love with science

Then you know that knowledge is endless.

The poet emphasizes that a person who wants perfection should acquire knowledge.

In fact, perfection is achieved through understanding the self and the world. This is achieved through continuous improvement of knowledge and skills. A person measures the level of knowledge and the level of his knowledge, he wants to know it. At such a time, tests come in handy not only for students, but also for everyone. In this sense, during his life, a person creates questions for himself in his mind, invents and solves their answers and options.

That is, when we look at the essence, in a broad sense, the test is also present in our daily life.

Creating a test is a systematic process that has several steps.

Determining the purpose of the test.

Defining domains and constructs.

Creation of specific features of the test.

Formation of test tasks based on the specific characteristics of the test.

Analysis of test assignments with the help of specialists and making corrections where necessary.

Carrying out initial approval of test tasks and making corrections where necessary.

Approving test tasks on a large scale.

Statistical analysis of test assignments based on approval results, exclusion of non-compliant tests.

Carrying out validity and reliability studies for the final version of the test.

Making recommendations for test results.

There are steps involved in creating a test, some of which are listed below. They consist of:

At the 1st stage, the purpose of the test is defined. For example, a test used to identify gaps in students' knowledge always includes points where they make mistakes.

In the 2nd step, the domains and constructs to be evaluated are defined. Several methods can be used for this. One of them is the analysis of the goals set in the educational standards.

In step 3, the test specification is created. The specification specifies how and how many test tasks each element of the domain and construct to be evaluated will be tested.

In the next stages, test tasks are created and analyzed by experts. In the analysis of the test assignments, attention is paid to the

compliance with the rules of test preparation, comprehensibility, and accuracy.

At the 6th stage, the preliminary approval of the test tasks is carried out.

These steps are essential in creating any test. One of them is approval. In order to check the suitability of the created tests, approval is carried out. Assignments that do not meet the requirements are revised.

Approbation is a process that is conducted in order to identify inaccuracies and errors in the test, and at the next stages, the test tasks are approved on a large scale.

The purpose of probate is to ensure that the task is appropriate for the purpose of the test, the audience of the test takers, and the test specifications, and to ensure that they are clear and understandable.

After that, based on the approval results, tests that do not meet the requirements are

determined and they are re-edited. Creating test assignments requires a lot of responsibility. If certain rules are not followed during the preparation of the test, the results of the test may be mistrusted. As a result, the public's attitude towards the test and its results weakens.

Standardization ensures that tests are relevant to the local environment and that science-based conclusions can be drawn. Tests and their standards, reliability levels, the test environment and the results obtained from the test takers will be a suitable basis for experts. It serves to create an opportunity to improve the quality of the test processes conducted in our republic, to expand scientific research in the discovery of new ideas, and to introduce new knowledge.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Kuychiyeva M.A. Biologiya fanini o'qitishda fanlararo bog'lanishlarning o'rni va ahamiyati // Zamonaviy ta'lim ilmiy-amaliy ommabop jurnal. - Toshkent, 2019. - №5 (78). - B. 34-37. (13.00.00; №10)
2. Kuychiyeva M.A. Tabiiy fanlar o'qituvchilarining kompetentligi va kasbiy layoqatini rivojlantirish masalalari // Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti Ilmiy axborotlari. - Toshkent, 2021. - №1-son. - B. 53-57. (13.00.00; №32).
3. Kuychiyeva M.A. Use of Interdisciplinary Relationships In The Formation Of Competences In Biology Students // CONVERTER 2021 www.converter-magazine.info. - P. 485-489. (№10. ISSN:0010-8189). (subscription@converter-magazine.info)
4. Kuychiyeva M.A. // Organization of Experimental Works on the Development of Professional and Methodical Competence of Future Biology Teachers // Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. Open Access, Peer Reviewed Journals. 2022. ISSN (E): 2795-739, - P.19-21. (№7. SJIF; IF-8.115) (www.geniusjournals.org)
5. Kuychiyeva M.A., Eshmatova D. Development of Professional and Methodical Competence of Future Biology Teachers in Extracurricular Activities // Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. 2022. ISSN:2776-0979, - P. 617-621. (№12. SJIF; IF-7.565). (<https://wos.academiascience.org>)
6. Ergashevich, R. U. (2019). Cognitive tasks in educational-upbringing process on biology. International scientific review, (LVII), 60-61.
7. Shakhmurova, G. A., Rakhmatov, U. E., & Saidjanova, U. S. A complex of entertaining tasks and exercises on Biology as one means of enhancing the cognitive skills of students. Asia life sciences, 30(1), 87-97.